

FLESH ON FIRE: THE DEVASTATING CONSEQUENCES OF TOXIC EPIDERMAL NECROLYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN) is a rare but potentially fatal adverse drug reaction characterized by widespread epidermal necrosis and detachment involving more than 30% of the body surface area. This is a rare case of cefpodoxime-induced TEN in a pediatric patient and emphasize the importance of early diagnosis and supportive care. **Case Summary:** An eight-year-old female presented with multiple vesiculobullous lesions involving the trunk, limbs, and mucosa following three days of cefpodoxime therapy for fever. The drug was discontinued immediately, and the child was managed in the intensive care unit with intravenous fluids, systemic corticosteroids, and intravenous immunoglobulin. Based on WHO-UMC criteria, the adverse drug reaction was categorized as probable. Gradual re-epithelialization of lesions occurred

over two weeks, with complete recovery after 21 days. **Conclusion:** TEN is a dermatological emergency that requires prompt drug withdrawal and multidisciplinary supportive care. This case highlights the potential of even commonly prescribed antibiotics like cefpodoxime to cause severe adverse drug reactions.

KEYWORDS: Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis, Cefpodoxime, Adverse Drug Reaction, Cephalosporins, Stevens–Johnson Syndrome.

INTRODUCTION

Stevens–Johnson Syndrome (SJS) and Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN) are uncommon, yet severe forms of cutaneous adverse drug reactions associated with considerable morbidity and mortality. The estimated annual incidence in the general population ranges from 1 to 6 cases per million for SJS and 0.4 to 1.2 cases per million for TEN.^[1]

Estimating the true incidence of SJS and TEN is challenging, as their rarity necessitates large population-based datasets. Hospital-based estimates are often limited in accuracy due to small sample sizes and reporting biases. Furthermore, establishing definitive diagnoses can be difficult, as the distinction between SJS, TEN, and erythema multiforme major (EMM) was historically unclear until an expert consensus group introduced standardized clinical classification criteria.^[2]

The underlying mechanism of SJS and TEN is believed to be an immune-mediated hypersensitivity reaction initiated by certain drugs or their reactive metabolites, resulting in extensive keratinocyte death. Cytotoxic T cells play a central role by activating apoptotic pathways involving Fas–Fas ligand interactions, granulysin release, and pro-inflammatory cytokines. Although therapeutic approaches have improved, these conditions continue to represent dermatological emergencies that demand rapid identification, immediate withdrawal of the causative agent, and coordinated multidisciplinary management to minimize morbidity and mortality.^[3]

CASE REPORT

An eight-year-old female child presented with multiple fluid-filled lesions over the trunk and limbs that rapidly progressed to involve the face, lips, and oral mucosa. She also complained of dysphagia and purulent ocular discharge. The child had been administered the antimicrobial agent cefpodoxime (100 mg twice daily) for fever with chills in an outpatient setting by a local practitioner outside, and was subsequently referred to our institution for further management. Lesions appeared after the third dose. There was no prior history of drug allergies or comorbidities.

On examination, she was febrile (102°F) with generalized erythematous rashes, erosions, and bullae covering approximately 35% of body surface area. Mucosal involvement was noted in the oral cavity and conjunctiva. Nikolsky's sign was positive. Laboratory investigations revealed leukocytosis (WBC 15,200/mm³) with normal liver and renal function tests.

Serology for HSV and *Mycoplasma pneumoniae* was negative. Cefpodoxime was withdrawn immediately. The patient was managed with intravenous fluids, electrolyte replacement, sterile wound dressings, ocular lubricants, systemic corticosteroids (methylprednisolone 1 mg/kg/day), and intravenous immunoglobulin (IV-IG 1 g/kg/day for 3 days). Gradual re-epithelialization occurred within two weeks, with full recovery after 21 days. As per causality assessment, this adverse drug reaction is categorized as "Probable" according to WHO-UMC probability scale. According to Hartwig–Siegel severity scale, it was level 6 (Severe), and Schumock–Thornton scale indicated it as "Not Preventable."

Figure 1: Extensive mucocutaneous involvement in cefpodoxime-induced Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN).

DISCUSSION

As according to Chung *et al.*, TEN is an immunologically mediated reaction caused by extensive keratinocyte apoptosis. The pathogenesis involves activation of cytotoxic T lymphocytes and Fas–Fas ligand interaction, leading to epidermal necrosis.^[4] Cefpodoxime, a third-generation cephalosporin, was identified as the causative agent in this case. Although

such antibiotics are generally well-tolerated, Boroda *et al.* and Kumar *et al.* have reported similar instances of severe hypersensitivity reactions associated with cephalosporin use.^[5,6]

According to Lee *et al.* (2023), prompt initiation of immunomodulatory treatment, when applied judiciously, may reduce mortality and enhance recovery in SJS/TEN. Despite better insight into disease mechanisms and improved management, mortality remains substantial, underscoring the importance of early recognition, timely drug withdrawal, and collaborative patient care.^[7] Supportive care remains the cornerstone of therapy, focusing on hemodynamic stability, infection prevention, and wound healing. The SCORTEN system is used for prognostic assessment, with scores ≥ 3 indicating high mortality. In this case, early diagnosis, prompt drug withdrawal, and supportive therapy resulted in favorable recovery.

CONCLUSION

Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis is a life-threatening dermatological emergency requiring high clinical suspicion. Even widely used antibiotics such as cefpodoxime may cause this severe reaction. Early recognition, drug withdrawal, and intensive multidisciplinary care are crucial for survival.

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